

I am what I am: A discourse analysis of SDCA nursing students in the clinical area

Christian S. Tu*

School of Health Science Professions, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding Author: ctu@sdca.edu.ph

Abstract

Clinical and classroom instructors have a significant effort in developing different strategies and resources to help the students to learn in the classroom setting and applied in the clinical area what they have thought to them. Despite these attempts, there is some empirical data in nursing education that indicates these approaches are beneficial. This study analyzed the reflections of nursing students of St. Dominic College of Asia who experience in the classroom as they apply their practice in clinical settings. Six (6) participants were involved in the study. Using feedback diaries from semi-structured interviews, a discourse analysis founded on Foucauldian concepts regarding technology of the self and governmentality was carried out. Based on the results of the study, reflection among nursing students is also seen to facilitate discussion and problem-solving around workplace issues. It was also discovered that many students learn from their clinical instructors as well as the nursing procedures from the clinical environment. The remarkable learning experiences may be applied to their future profession as a healthcare provider.

Keywords: Discourse analysis; nursing students; clinical area.

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Introduction

Clinical and classroom instructors have made a significant effort in developing different strategies and resources to help the students learn in the classroom setting and apply in the clinical area what they have thought to them. Some students think critically about multifaceted and evolving situations based on classroom management. Despite these attempts, there is some empirical data in nursing education that indicates these approaches are beneficial. However, some nurse educators have suggested that during the course of the nursing degree, nursing students' capacity for critical thinking might actually decrease.

According to Balabagno (2014), critical thinking is defined as the ability to thrive in an ambiguous construct, so preparing students for a constantly evolving system of demands and maintaining the instructors' motivation in helping students develop their critical thinking skills across all educational levels. In addition, Tyczkowski et al. (2015) said that clinical experience is a vital and important component of a student nurse's education, according to several individuals involved in nursing education. Because they give nursing students the chance to engage with actual people in real-life situations, theory and practical practice are crucial to their education. Students can only put their theoretical knowledge into practice, hone their psychomotor abilities, and build their socialization for their future roles in the clinical context.

For a range of educational goals, nursing students visit locations in a novel setting. Students frequently build up adaptability, flexibility, and group sociability throughout the clinical immersion experience. The students' understanding of the things they are studying is improved, and their perspective is broadened by this encounter. Students get the chance to observe firsthand dynamics and cultural processes through cooperative work and clinical immersion experiences (Fowler et al., 2018; Lane et al., 2013). To impart the best knowledge, abilities, and attitudes, healthcare educators must demonstrate proficiencies in their clinical practices and competences (Albarqouni et al., 2018; Lane et al., 2013).

Nursing educators are dedicated to creating unique teaching approaches that help students become culturally competent, despite the lack of research in this field. Undergraduate and graduate nursing experiences in clinical settings are limited due to time constraints; however, students utilized their time to study to develop such competencies, including knowledge, skills, and attitudes (Lee et al., 2018; Missen et al., 2016).

Given the rapid growth of the nursing population all over the world, nursing students are expected to provide more skilled nursing care, with the clinical instructor's attentive guidance functioning as a guide. Although these clinical practices allow students to develop attitudes related to the humanization of care aside from gaining new knowledge and enhancing already learned techniques (González-García et al., 2020), some nursing students described their negative feelings during clinical trainings, which could affect their emotional and social well-being.

By enlightening nurses' image through their experiences in clinical settings, they are facing different problems and difficulties, especially during clinical exposure. Douglas et al. (2011) said that difficulties encountered by student nurses in the clinical setting may lead to failure to learn and rejection of the nursing profession. As the title suggests, the researcher's focus in this paper will be on the impact of nurses' relationships with their mentors as they reflect on their work. Rather than making a case for or against reflective activities, the researcher used the Foucauldian concept of power to examine how these practices function within discourse to influence future nursing behaviors that are desired. This kind of attention is crucial because it clarifies for us the complexity of reflection and its various interpretations and implications when used in discursive language, since it is not often made visible in reflection narratives. The researcher's main goal is to analyze reflection as discourse and produce a desirable outcome for students, especially in the nursing field.

The researcher of this study analyzed the reflections of nursing students of St. Dominic College of Asia who experience in the classroom as they apply their practice in clinical settings. Specifically, the researcher sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the themes that can be formulated out of the following sub-questions?
 - What have you learned?
 - Where can you apply it?
 - What are the hindrances that you have encountered?
2. What are the remarkable experiences for SDCA student nurses?
3. How do the nursing students reflect to their experiences?

Significance of the Study

This study would be beneficial to the following recipients:

Student Nurses. It may bring awareness to nursing students to be ready for their clinical exposure and must be able to face the possible challenges that they encounter and be open to the potential that they themselves would be the key to initiating possible changes that may affect the nursing culture.

School Administrators. Through this study, the school administrators may possibly enlighten nurses' image by supporting different programs for nursing students.

Future Researchers. This study may serve as a reference for future proponents related to the topic.

Research Methodology

Prior to the proposed information gathering, the researcher utilized bracketing to separate personal perceptions and feelings regarding the proposed study so as to avoid contaminating the phenomena that were under study. No guide questions were prepared, but a grand tour question was raised, and the succeeding questions may depend on the response of the informants so as to prevent any presumption that may lead to biases. The researcher utilized convenience sampling in choosing the informants.

Research Design

Using feedback diaries from semi-structured interviews, a discourse analysis founded on Foucauldian concepts regarding the technology of the self and governmentality was carried out. Discourse analysis comes in a variety of forms, from studies of discourse and power to those that concentrate primarily on language or language and interaction (Nixon & Power, 2007). The researcher's primary attention is on what the participant has to say in their feedback journal, how it can be said, and what discursive impacts these kinds of speech patterns have. More specifically, it focuses on how discourse—that is, linguistic patterns—forms the intended result of supervision through education.

Discourse analysis is used to refer to a broad range of theoretical perspectives and analytical frameworks. One of the approaches of qualitative research was utilized by the researcher in its attempt to analyze the reflection as discourse of SDCA nursing students as they reflect on their classroom instructor as applied to clinical settings. The proponent of this study utilized the learning feedback diary provided by the student as part of the lecture requirements vis-à-vis the clinical area. According to Polit and Beck (2017), discourse analysis explores the connections between knowledge, power, and social practices. In summary, it is concerned with the context-specific meaning and structure of communication acts, whether they are overt or covert. Discourse-based research comes in a variety of forms.

Research Participants

A convenience sampling technique was utilized wherein the researcher gathered feedback diaries from different students under their different nursing instructors. Using reflective techniques to examine before learning was one of the program's primary ideas. About one third of the population or 26 informants were chosen for the program. Feedback diaries were collected, with sampling based on their availability at the time of transcription. The sample consisted of 26 informants but only six (6) has reached the degree of saturation.

Data Collection

Data were collected between October 2018 and August 2019 using guided questions from the feedback diary. In total, five semi-structured guide questions by the researcher were utilized: (1) What have you learned? (2) Where can you apply it? (3) What are the hindrances you have encountered? (4) What is your suggestion or recommendation? Prior to conducting this research, the informants will be selected based on the researchers' choices. The informants submitted their feedback diary as part of their requirements in lecture and in the clinical area. The researcher utilized the guide questions in the feedback diary.

Data Analysis

The epistemological premise of this discourse analysis approach, which draws inspiration from Foucault, is that discourse shapes reality, and the only way we can understand how discourse shapes reality is by examining text (either written or spoken material, such as a learning feedback journal) (Fuller et al., 2016). As a result, the researcher's transcription was understood to be texts that discourse both produces and is composed of. Consequently, this article may be seen as a discourse that can be dissected and examined as a text that makes statements about other texts (thereby forming subjectivity).

Results and Discussion

In this chapter, the discourse analysis is presented as follows: the classroom lecture of reflection as what BSN students learned from their concept, followed by an analysis of the desirable outcome in the clinical area or answering the question voluntarily where they could apply this learning, and third if they are experiencing a hindrance to their practice. In the third section, appraisals were analyzed as such. Based on the theoretical framework, the questions guiding the analysis to formulate a theme are: How do SDCA nursing students reflect in their classroom and in clinical settings, and does it affect their practice professionally?

Reflection of Nursing Students in Theory

The texts that were examined present reflection as a beneficial activity that ought to improve nursing practice. In addition to being considered beneficial in groups, reflection is also seen as facilitating discussion and problem-solving around workplace issues. Thus, people may benefit from one another:

“We learned a lot from theory, and we make sure that we could applied all learnings as soon as we need it in the future professionally. Most of our instructors are competent enough to share their expertise in the chosen field of profession. However some of our clinical instructors are very strict. We didn't know how we will approach them, but we make sure everything is under control.” (BSN A)

The way that individual reflection is presented is being compared with group reflection. The person is inspired to share their expertise and make it visible to all through this kind of reflective practice. A person may have their own ideas. Individual reflection is also shown as something good that enables one to work on oneself in order to become a desirable learner:

“If we haven't learned anything from our lecture we do self-study because If our professors can't impart knowledge I make sure that we can do it by reading books like in Medical and Surgical Nursing, Maternal and Child Nursing, and Community and Public Health. We are here to learn not to blame others.” (BSN B)

The concept of introspection as a desired result is developed in this literature on a personal level. A person should examine themselves by thinking back on their everyday activities and assessing what is beneficial and what is harmful. Such narratives are part of several interviews. As another group of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) wrote:

“Some of our clinical instructors do a lot of based routines especially in the clinical areas, as they allow us to do a charting, carrying out doctor's orders, and making bedside manners. I know one time one of the clinical instructors, they teach this specific procedure like central venous pressure (CVP) readings, nasogastric tube (NGT) insertions, and Interferential Current Therapy (IFC). After an hour they applied it immediately to the patient; we may do it easily because of the freshness of this theory in our mind.” (BSN C)

One student stated in the text that they ought to deviate from their daily routine in order to improve as nurses in the coming years. The process of acknowledging past knowledge leads to introspection, which awakens informants and helps them achieve a positive outcome.

Three themes were also developed based on the responses of the nursing students according to the learning feedback diary. These are: (1) Learning with the Clinical Procedures; (2) Application of the Nursing Procedures; and (3) Obstacles in the Clinical Area.

In terms of learning clinical procedures, this theme shows the motivation to learn for students. According to one student, this task allows the nursing instructors to prepare the students for exposure to nursing procedures prior to their application. In terms of the application of the nursing procedures, this theme shows the interest of the participants. One student shared that from their clinical skills and teaching enhancement, students prepare themselves in handling patients with the nursing procedures.

In terms of obstacles in the clinical area, three subcategories were developed. These are ineffective communication, inadequate readiness, and emotional reactions. First is the ineffective communication. This is essentially most important among other themes because it deals with nurses, doctors, and other persons involved in the hospital. Mostly, the response of the students is that they tend to ineffectively communicate with the clinical instructors. It stresses themselves out to communicate with other staff.

The second is the inadequate readiness. Teachers need to prepare their students to be involved in the clinical setting; however, students were quite unprepared in their respective areas. Lastly are the emotional reactions. In line with this, emotional reactions from nursing students were discovered, and they seemed to develop an inferiority complex because more male nurses are prepared than females.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, many students learn from their clinical instructors as well as the nursing procedures in the clinical environment. Participants encountered different obstacles in the clinical area. The teachers prepare their students for dealing with those obstacles. The remarkable learning experiences may be applied to their future profession as healthcare providers. Clinical instructors have been good role models to the students as they apply all the learning, applications, and remarkable ideas. Aside from using discourse analysis adapted from Michel Foucault, future researchers may also use grounded theory for further research.

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